

5-Aryl-6-Mercaptobenzyl-3-Phenyl-4-Phenylimino-2-Thio Tetrahydro-1,3,5-Triazines

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S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride and S-benzyl aryl isothiocarbamides on reaction in boiling benzene medium has been shown to afford 5-aryl-6-mercaptobenzyl-3-phenyl-4-phenylimino-2-thio tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazines. A probable mechanism has been suggested.

INTERACTION of S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride and aryl thiocarbamides in boiling benzene medium leading to 1,3,5-triazines has been reported earlier¹ and the structure II was suggested for the product of this reaction. The 1,3,5-triazine (IIa) on benzylation with benzyl chloride has been shown to afford its mercaptobenzyl derivative. Therefore, it appeared worthwhile to investigate the reaction of the above isothiocarbamoyl chloride and S-benzyl phenyl isothiocarbamide in boiling benzene medium, which is likely to afford the same mercaptobenzyl derivative reported earlier¹. Interaction of S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride and S-benzyl aryl isothiocarbamides in boiling benzene medium forms the subject of matter of this communication.

where R = (a) phenyl, (b) *p*-tolyl and (c) *p*-chlorophenyl

The reaction (where aryl = phenyl) afforded a solid, C₂₃H₂₂N₄S₂, m.p. 136°, accompanied by evolution of hydrogen chloride. The yield of the product could be increased appreciably when the ratio of the reactants was 2 : 1 molar proportion.

The product was found stable to hot alcoholic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide and 4% boiling aqueous alkali. It was not desulphurised by hot alkali plumbite solution. Its IR spectrum indicated the presence of C=S, N-C=N and S-CH₂Ph bands and also an isotriazine structure². As expected a ring -NH band was not noticed in spectrum.

On the basis of above facts the product C₂₃H₂₂N₄S₂ appears to be most probably a mercaptobenzyl isotriazine derivative for which two formulations IIIa or IVa are possible.

But the structure (IVa) viz. 2-mercaptobenzyl-1,5-diphenyl-4-phenylimino-6-thio tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazine was ruled out for this product on the basis of its independent synthesis. The synthesis was performed as follows :

2-S-Benzyliso-4-S-ethyliso-1,5-diphenyl biuret (VIa), (obtained by the reaction of 2-S-benzyliso-1,5-diphenyl-4-thiobiuret (V)^{3,4} and ethyl iodide in boiling ethanol followed by basification with dilute aqueous ammonia), on reaction with phenyl isothiocyanate in acetone medium and subsequent cyclisation, eliminated ethyl mercaptan and formed IVa. (Schem 1).

III

IV

The structure 6-mercaptobenzyl-3,5-diphenyl-4-phenylimino-2-thio tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazine (IVa) therefore, most probably represents the product with m.p. 136°.

It is evident from the reaction that two moles of S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride reacts with one mole of S-benzyl phenyl isothiocarbamide with loss of a sulphur atom. This sulphur was not eliminated as an elemental sulphur¹, but most probably as sulphur halide.

As expected, the compound with m.p. 136° was found identical in all respects with the free base of mercaptobenzyl derivative reported in our earlier communication¹.

Where R = (a) phenyl (b) *p*-tolyl

Scheme 1

On extending the reaction of *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbonyl chloride to *S*-benzyl *p*-tolyl and *p*-chlorophenyl isothiocarbamides under the similar reaction conditions the related product IIIb and IIIc respectively have been isolated.

The compound IVb (where R=*p*-tolyl) was also synthesised by procedure analogous to that for IVa by taking *S*-benzyl *p*-tolyl isothiocarbamide in place of *S*-benzyl phenyl isothiocarbamide.

As the reaction product of *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbonyl chloride and *S*-benzyl phenyl isothiocarbamide in boiling benzene medium was identical with the free base of mercaptobenzyl derivative of 1,3,5-triazine described in our earlier work¹, structure IIIa appeared more suitable for the product and not IVa as suggested earlier. Similarly, the structure I and not II will be more appropriate for the reaction products of *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbonyl chloride and aryl thiocarbamides in boiling benzene medium.

Mechanism of Reaction :

The mechanism of formation of III has been investigated in detail and two distinct intermediate stages have been isolated.

For example, formation of IIIa (where R=phenyl) takes place as follows :

One mole of *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbonyl chloride, when reacts with one mole of *S*-benzyl phenyl isothiocarbamide in cold benzene medium gives an

unstable intermediate product⁵ (VIIa). The structure (VIIIa) for unstable product has been ruled out because this on ring closure cannot give 4-aryl-3-mercaptobenzyl-5-phenylimino-1, 2, 4-thiadiazolines IXa. The more structure XIa cannot be ruled out for this product but formation of IIIa from this will be a multistep process.

The unstable product (VIIa) on reaction with a fresh mole of *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbonyl chloride in refluxing benzene medium, eliminated hydrogen chloride and a clear solution is obtained. On distilling out benzene, a semisolid mass was left, which on trituration several times with petroleum ether converted into a low melting unstable solid, m.p. 65°. This unstable solid was most probably 2,6-diphenyl-4-mercaptobenzyl-3-phenyl tetrahydro-1, 3, 5-thiadiazine intermediate (Xa). Because on treatment with alcohol it gave IIIa, m.p. 136°, identified on the basis of undepressed m.m.p. with IIIa obtained by the reaction of *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbonyl chloride and *S*-benzyl phenyl isothiocarbamide directly.

The mechanism of the reaction is shown in scheme 2.

The presence of SCl_2 however, could not be established. This might be due to its high reactivity towards moisture.

Similar types of intermediate stages VIIb, VIIc and Xb and Xc have been isolated in the stepwise reactions of *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbonyl chloride and *S*-benzyl *p*-tolyl and *S*-benzyl *p*-chlorophenyl isothiocarbamides also.

Where R = (a) phenyl (b) *p*-tolyl (c) *p*-chlorophenyl

Scheme 2

Experimental

The required *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride was prepared by the method described earlier⁶. The *S*-benzyl aryl isothiocarbamides have been prepared by the benzylation of an appropriate aryl thiocarbamide followed by basification with dilute aqueous ammonia.

1. Interaction of *S*-Chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride and *S*-benzyl aryl isothiocarbamides in boiling benzene medium.

Details of a typical experiment (where aryl=phenyl) are as follows:

When *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride (25 g) and *S*-benzyl phenyl isothiocarbamide (12 g) were allowed to react in refluxing benzene (100 ml) for three hours, evolution of hydrogen chloride was observed. On distilling out benzene a syrupy mass was left behind which on repeated washing with petroleum ether afforded a semisolid. The semisolid on treatment with cold ethanol dissolved and immediately a solid product was separated (18 g)⁷; crystals from aqueous acetone/acetic acid, m.p. 136° (Found: C, 69.75; H, 4.40; N, 11.67; S, 13.23. C₂₈H₂₂N₄S₂ requires; C, 70.29; H, 4.60; N, 11.71; S, 13.38%).

This product was found stable to hot alcoholic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide and 4% boiling aqueous alkali. It was not found desulphurisable when boiled with alkali plumbite solution. On heating odours of benzyl mercaptan and phenyl isothiocyanate were perceptible.

The IR spectrum of this compound showed the presence of C=S (1164 cm⁻¹); N-C=N (1616 cm⁻¹); S-CH₂PH (1215 cm⁻¹) bands. Another band at (1550 cm⁻¹) was most probably due to 1,3,5-triazine ring system. One more band at 750 cm⁻¹ probably indicated the presence of an isotriazine ring². The absence of a band due to cyclic-NH was noteworthy.

On the basis of the above facts this product with m.p. 136° has been assigned the structure 6-mercapto-benzyl-3, 5-diphenyl-4-phenylimino-2-thio tetrahydro 1,3,5-triazine (IIa). Another possible structure for this product, i.e. 2-mercaptobenzyl-1,5-diphenyl-4-phenylimino 6-thio tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazine(IVa) has been ruled out on the basis of its independent synthesis.

S-chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride (25 g) also reacted with *S*-benzyl *p*-tolyl isothiocarbamide (13 g) and *S* benzyl *p*-chlorophenyl isothiocarbamide (14 g) in refluxing benzene medium in an analogous manner afforded the related products IIIb (10 g); m.p. 145° (Found: N, 11.17; S, 13.13. C₂₉H₂₄N₄S₂ requires; N, 11.38; S, 13.00% and IIIc (18 g) m.p. 139° (Found: N, 10.76; S, 12.27. C₂₈H₂₁N₄S₂Cl requires; N, 10.92; S, 12.48%), respectively.

2. Synthesis of 2-mercaptobenzyl-1,5-diphenyl-4-phenylimino-6-thio tetrahydro-1, 3, 5-triazine (IVa)

2-*S*-benzyl iso-1,5-diphenyl-4-thiobiuret (VIa) was converted into 2-*S*-benzyliso-4-*S*-ethyliso-1,5-diphenyl biuret (Va) m.p. 70°, by heating the former (10 g) under reflux with ethyl iodide (6ml) in ethanol (30ml) followed

by basification with dilute ammonium hydroxide. A mixture of Va (5 g), phenylisothiocyanate (3 ml) and acetone (40 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 hours, when evolution of ethyl mercaptan was observed. On evaporation of acetone, a sticky residue was obtained which on repeated washing with petroleum ether afforded a solid (3 g), crystallised from aqueous acetic acid, m.p. 213° (Found: N, 11.53; S, 13.28. $C_{28}H_{22}N_4S_2$ requires; N, 11.71; S, 13.38%).

It was found non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkali plumbite solution. On heating odours of benzyl mercaptan and phenyl isothiocyanate, were quite perceptible. The IR spectrum of this compound showed the presence of C=S (1160 cm^{-1}), S-CH₂Ph (1200 cm^{-1}) and N-C=N (1640 cm^{-1}). It also indicated the presence of two bands at 1575 and 60 cm^{-1} , characteristic of isotriazine ring system². Here also band due to-NH was found absent.

The related compound IVb (where R = *p*-tolyl), m.p. 228° (Found: N, 11.08; S, 13.18. $C_{29}H_{24}N_4S_2$ requires; N, 11.38; S, 13.00%) has also been synthesised by taking S-benzyl *p*-tolyl isothiocarbamide in place of S-benzyl phenyl isothiocarbamide. The synthesised IVb was found completely different from the product (IIIb) obtained directly by the interaction of S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride and S-benzyl *p*-tolyl isothiocarbamide (*vide supra*).

Mechanism

(a) *Interaction of S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride and S-benzyl aryl isothiocarbamides in 1:1 ratio: Formation of VII:*

Details of a typical experiment (where aryl = phenyl) are as follows:

When to a well cooled solution of S-benzyl phenylisothiocarbamide in benzene (24 g in 100 ml) was added gradually a benzene solution of S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride (25 g in 50 ml) and the mixture maintained around 5° by cooling in freezing mixture, a reaction with evolution of hydrogen chloride was noticed. After standing for several hours, a solid was deposited. The solid was quickly washed several times with benzene followed by petroleum ether, when an unstable product $C_{21}H_{18}N_8S_2Cl_2$ (VIIa) was obtained (Found: N, 9.01; S, 14.34. $C_{21}H_{18}N_8S_2Cl_2$ requires, N, 9.33; S, 14.22%). It was acidic in nature and was found desulphurisable with hot alkali plumbite solution. On heating it decomposed and smell of benzylmercaptan was quite perceptible.

Similarly, S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride on reaction with S-benzyl *p*-tolyl isothiocarbamide and S-benzyl *p*-chlorophenyl isothiocarbamide under analogous reaction conditions afforded related VIIb m.p. 120° (d) and VIIc m.p. 86° (d).

(b) *Reaction of VII with a fresh mole of S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride: Formation of X:*

Following are the details of a typical reaction of VIIa with 1 mole of S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride:

A mixture of VIIa (35 g) and S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride (25 g) was refluxed for 2 hours. During the progress of heating gradually V Ia went into solution and evolution of hydrogen chloride was observed. After distilling out benzene, a sticky semisolid was obtained, which on trituration several times with petroleum ether and standing turned into a reddish brown solid (22 g), m.p. 62° (d). This solid was purified by redissolving in benzene and precipitating it with petroleum ether, m.p. 65° (d) (Found: N, 10.84; S, 12.48. $C_{28}H_{22}N_4S_2$ requires; N, 11.62; S, 13.28%). It was found unstable when exposed to atmosphere. This was expected to be 2,6-diphenyl-4-mercaptobenzyl-3-phenyl tetrahydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine (Xa). This on treatment with ethanol first dissolved and then reprecipitated as stable white solid, crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 136°. This was found identical with the reaction product, m.p. 136° (IIIa), obtained directly by the reaction of S-benzyl phenyl isothiocarbamide and S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride.

Similarly VIIb and VIIc on further reaction with S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride afforded the related Xb and Xc m.p. 53° (d) and 71° (d) respectively. As expected both were very unstable. These also on treatment with aqueous ethanol afforded IIIb and IIIc respectively.

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